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Patient-Independent Epileptic Seizure Detection with Reduced EEG Channels and Deep Recurrent Neural Networks

Nadine El-Dajani ^{1,*}, Tim Friedrich Lutz Wilhelm ¹, Jan Baumann ², Rainer Surges ²

¹ Communication Acoustics, Department for Medical Physics and Acoustics and Cluster of Excellence Hearing4all, Carl von Ossietzky Universität Oldenburg, 26129 Oldenburg, Germany; bernd.meyer@uni-oldenburg.com (B.T.M.)

² Klinik und Poliklinik für Epileptologie, University Clinic, 53127 Bonn, Germany; rainer.surges@ukbonn.de (R.S.)

* Correspondence: nadine.el-dajani@uni-oldenburg.de

Abstract: Epileptic seizures affect around 1% of people worldwide and have an enormous impact on the quality of life as well as the health of each patient. Electroencephalography (EEG) is widely used to diagnose epilepsy and detect seizures. Automatic detection and documentation of epileptic seizures using EEG signals would help neurologists evaluate the course of disease of each patient individually. As scalp EEG systems are not suited to be worn in everyday life situations, there is a need for mobile EEG systems to permanently record EEG signals. An approach for such mobile devices consists of using behind-the-ear (BTE) electrodes, leading to a reduction in electrode channels. To address this reduction, we investigated the influence of different scalp EEG channel arrangements on the detection of epileptic seizures. Raw EEG signals have been used as input for a long short-term memory (LSTM) recurrent neural network (RNN), as well as a combination of a convolutional neural network (CNN) and LSTM to classify ictal and inter-ictal phases. When using all channels of the 10–20 EEG cap system, the CNN-LSTM model achieved a sensitivity of 73%, with fewer than two seizures being falsely detected per hour. The usage of BTE channels as input to the proposed epileptic seizure detection produced a promising sensitivity of 68% with around 10 false alarms per hour.

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1. Introduction

Epilepsy is a widely spread neurological disorder characterized by unforeseen seizures, which not only drastically decreases quality of life but can also be life-threatening [1]. Since the occurrence of seizures during the day and night time cannot be predicted, the disease has an enormous impact on the everyday life of epilepsy patients. Constant therapy with correct medication can help to decrease the frequency and intensity of seizures and therefore increase the patients' health and quality of life significantly. To ensure an optimal treatment for patients, precise documentation of the seizure events, i.e., ictal phases, is desirable. Yet, only 26.8% of focal impaired awareness seizures (FIAS) and 73.8% of focal awareness seizures (FAS) were manually documented by patients in a representative study [2]. Thus, the development of an automated epileptic seizure detection (ESD) system classifying ictal and inter-ictal, i.e., non-seizure phases, is regarded as increasingly important for research in the field of epilepsy as well as for clinical applications.

An established way to detect and diagnose epilepsy is to measure and record the electrical potentials of brain activity through electroencephalography (EEG). An epileptic

seizure accompanied by a change in muscle activity is categorized as a motor seizure, whereas non-motor seizures do not influence muscle activity. This category is important for EEG-based classification since changes in muscle potentials result in very different patterns captured through EEG. Figure 1 shows an example frame of signal characteristics for non-motor (left) and motor (right) seizures taken from one patient's seizures out of the EPItect data set (see Section 2.5), which is used in this study. While non-motor seizures are characterized by slow rhythmic patterns, motor seizures cause irregular patterns with high amplitudes.

Figure 1. Top: example frame (23 s) of non-motor seizure (a) as well as motor seizure (b) signal patterns of left side EEG channels recordings from the EPItect data set. Bottom: three-second part of the above-shown signal of channel F3 in the range of $U = 0$ to $150 \mu\text{V}$ and $U = -200$ to $200 \mu\text{V}$ for non-motor and motor seizures, respectively.

In clinical studies, full-size caps that cover the head surface with electrodes are regularly used; a popular norm for placing and referencing these electrodes is the 10–20 EEG cap system [3]. The electrode arrangement of this system provides a good coverage of cortical activity. However, such cap systems are not suited for everyday and mobile use and are therefore mainly restricted to clinical environments. Only a few seizures can be recorded with these systems since seizures do not occur regularly and the probability of patients having seizures during the limited recording time in clinical environments is low. A mobile EEG system would enable constant recording of brain activities and therefore capture more seizure events. Mobile systems for seizure detection often consist of intracranial [4] or subcutaneous [5] EEG and are therefore associated with highly invasive surgery. To avoid the risks accompanying surgical operations and to provide documentation systems that can be used outside a clinical context, approaches for non-invasive mobile EEG systems were developed, such as behind-the-ear (BTE) electrode systems [6]. With these systems, referred to as cEEGrids, EEG signals can be reliably captured. As temporal lobe epilepsy (TLE) is the most common focal epilepsy type [7], most seizures can be captured with temporal lobe EEG channels, as provided in cEEGrids and other mobile behind-the-ear EEG systems.

In the context of seizure detection, two-channel BTE systems have been explored in combination with support vector machines [8,9]. Gu et al. [8] examined EEG signals of BTE channels referenced to contralateral and unilateral BTE channels. It was shown that contralateral referencing of BTE channels leads to higher power spectral density than other channel-to-reference configurations of scalp EEG. Moreover, the comparison of BTE and scalp EEG channel signals to electrooculography indicated that eye-blinking artifacts

have a negligible effect on BTE electrode signals. Vandecasteele et al. [9] explored both patient-dependent and -independent EEG signals and reported that a visual inspection of BTE signals allows the identification of ictal phases with a low false alarm rate (<0.5 per day) for the patient-specific classification. This hints at the suitability of BTE channels for mobile EEG systems, which implies that solutions exist that are relatively easy to attach for recording EEG data. However, the above-mentioned studies do not apply deep machine learning to ESD (which might bear large potential given the success of deep learning methods in other fields) but combine support vector machines with preprocessing steps, such as artifact removal and feature extraction. Also, differences between motor- and non-motor seizures were not reported.

Aside from support vector machines [8,10], a wide range of other machine learning approaches has been suggested for automatic seizure detection, e.g., random forest [11], or k-nearest-neighbor algorithms [12]. However, these machine learning approaches usually require a well-designed feature extraction stage and are less suited for processing raw time series data. The same is true for several deep learning approaches, such as convolutional neural networks (CNNs) (see, for instance, [13] or [14]) or deep belief networks [15]. CNNs have been shown to be very reliable in terms of multi-dimensional signal classification such as image recognition. Through the use of learned two-dimensional filters, CNNs are capable of learning local dependencies from data samples, which might also be useful for pattern recognition in temporally localized ESD patterns across EEG channels.

Recurrent neural networks (RNNs) are known to be especially useful for directly processing time series data [16] and should therefore be a good candidate for classifying raw EEG signals. One issue with RNNs can occur during training since gradients calculated during the backpropagation training procedure can vanish or explode, i.e., the training does not converge. A modified version of RNNs namely the long short-term memory (LSTM) networks proposed by Hochreiter and Schmidhuber [17] addresses this problem, making it the better choice for long-term sequences.

Hussein et al. [18] proposed an LSTM-based neural network for ESD and used the open-source Bonn University EEG database [19] as input to the ESD model. The database contains scalp EEG data collected from non-epileptic volunteers as well as intracranial EEG (iEEG) data of epilepsy patients with a balanced amount of ictal and inter-ictal phases. In their study, Hussein et al. [18] corrupted the raw EEG data by adding noise to quantify the robustness of the model regarding common EEG artifacts, such as muscle and eye movement as well as power line interference. The model was designed as a single-channel model, i.e., classification decisions are derived from a single EEG signal at a time.

In related work, a variety of multi-channel deep learning approaches for ESD have been investigated, mostly based on feature extraction in combination with DNNs [13,20,21]. To address long-term dependencies as well as the multi-dimensional (or across-channel) aspects of EEG data, Golmohammadi et al. [22] combined a CNN with an LSTM network. Linear frequency cepstral coefficients of scalp EEG data from the TUH EEG Corpus [23] were passed through a two-dimensional CNN (2D-CNN) followed by a bidirectional LSTM network [24].

The contributions of the current study is as follows: In general, we explore patient-independent deep learning algorithms for classifying ictal and non-ictal phases from raw EEG data, i.e., without processing stages such as artifact removal, feature extraction, or adaptation to data from a specific patient. Specifically, we compare the performance obtained with clinical multi-channel data with electrodes that cover the scalp to results when only electrodes close to the ear are used. The latter scenario—which has not been explored before in the context of deep learning—should quantify the potential performance loss when electrode sets that are compatible with mobile scenarios are used. Second,

recurrent classifiers alone are used as a baseline and are combined with convolutional networks to determine if the different properties of algorithms are complementary and result in an average improvement. Finally, the differences between motor and non-motor signals (Figure 1) motivated a dedicated analysis of the two seizure types by training and testing our proposed system individually or with both seizure types combined. The results could have implications with mobile ESD in interaction with the specific type of seizures that a user suffers from.

2. Materials and Methods

Three deep learning models were compared with regard to classifying ictal and inter-ictal phases in raw scalp EEG data. Since EEG signals are time series data, recurrent neural networks are included in each model to account for temporal dependencies. The first one is based on the model presented by Hussein et al. [18] with single-channel data being fed into an LSTM which is therefore referred to as single-channel LSTM (sLSTM). Second, the model architecture is also used in a multi-channel fashion (mLSTM), for which electrode sets are defined (see below) and used as input data. While LSTMs account for temporal dependencies in the data set, CNNs can take across-channel correlation into account. Hence, the third model combines a CNN with the mLSTM model (CNN-LSTM). In our experiments, we opted for LSTMs rather than the simpler Gated Recurrent Units (GRUs) since the cell states and gating mechanisms in LSTMs could contribute to better handling of long-term dependencies in the data, which could be crucial for this specific task. Also, the LSTM output gate could allow better control of the information flow and a better handling of feature relevance. For applications with limited computational constraints, it would be interesting to explore GRUs as well. Note that transformer-based models were not considered due to the sequence length associated with EEG signals for seizure detection, which would have resulted in prohibitive computational costs and due to limitations of training data and class imbalance.

Different electrode channel-to-reference combinations were considered in this study, as presented in Table 1, to explore if the reduced amount of electrode channels in mobile EEG systems would influence the modeling approach, as well as which specific combination results in the best classification performance.

Table 1. Overview to the experimental methods.

Motor	Models	Channel Regions	Reference
motor m	CNN-LSTM	B, T, C, A	$\bar{B}, \bar{T}, \bar{A}$
non-motor n	mLSTM		
both $m\&n$	sLSTM	$T4$	$T3, \bar{B}, \bar{T}, \bar{A}$

For the single-channel model, the EEG signal of the electrode channel $T4$ was chosen as input to the model since temporal lobe channels appear to be especially important for seizure detection as indicated in the introduction. Four different electrode configurations were used as input to the two multi-channel approaches: B uses the behind-the-ear electrodes $T3$ and $T4$, the configuration T (channels near the temporal lobe) comprises channels $T3, T4, T5$, and $T6$; C refers to channels near the vertex ($C3, C4$, and Cz), and A refers to using all 21 channels of the 10–20 EEG cap system.

Regarding the reference for the voltage measured with the electrodes, different reference channels (or averages thereof) were considered: Channel signals were re-referenced to the arithmetic averages of the groups defined above, i.e., \bar{B}, \bar{T} , and \bar{A} . In the single-channel condition, channel $T4$ was additionally re-referenced with the contra-lateral channel $T3$, since related research found contra-lateral referencing to improve classification over using

an ipsi-lateral reference [8]. The average of Set C was not used as a reference since the central electrodes in this set are not compatible with BTE applications.

2.1. Re-Referencing

Each channel signal was re-referenced by subtracting the reference signal $r[n]$ from the originally recorded raw channel signal $x[n]$ resulting in the signal $y[n]$:

$$y[n]_{\alpha,\beta} = x_{\alpha}[n] - r_{\beta}[n], \quad (1)$$

where α and β refer to the index of the raw channel(s) and the (set of) reference channels, respectively. Thus, when processing channel set B referenced to \bar{A} , Equation (1) becomes

$$y[n]_{B,\bar{A}} = x_B[n] - r_{\bar{A}}[n]. \quad (2)$$

2.2. Neural Network Input Dimensions

The raw EEG signals from the EPItect data set have a duration of up to several hours. For classification, the data are segmented into frames used as model input. In pilot experiments, we systematically varied the frame duration from 1 to 24 s using frames without overlap and found a duration of 23 s to be optimal. At a sampling rate of 256 Hz, this corresponds to a length of $D = 5888$ samples, which we use as one frame. An input batch to the sLSTM consists of N frames and has the dimension $[N \times D \times L]$. To reduce the computational complexity of the model, it is beneficial to further subdivide these frames into L segments thus enabling parallel processing performed by the LSTM model. Following the hyperparameter optimization presented by Hussein et al. [18], we choose $L = 2$ for our experiments. The EEG frames are therefore reshaped from $[N \times D \times 1]$, where N is the total number of frames, to the dimension $[N \times D/2 \times 2]$ as shown in Figure 2 on the left.

For multi-channel input, the input dimension for a training batch is $[N \times D \times C]$, where C is the number of channels as shown on the right of Figure 2. For the forward run of the model (the classification step) $L = 1$ is chosen. For the multi-channel LSTM approach, the channel sets defined in Table 1 were used to train and test individual models.

For the CNN-LSTM architecture, the raw input data are first fed into the CNN component with an input dimension of $[N \times D \times C]$. We decided to keep $C = 22$ fixed for all configurations of multi-channel input. For channel sets other than Set A, this was implemented by duplicating and stacking channels until the required number of input channels was reached. This holds model parameters for the CNN part constant and also enables explicit feature padding on the EEG feature level, i.e., across-channel patterns between boundary channels could also be learned by the 2D filters from the CNN. Hence, the input dimension for the CNN-LSTM model is constant, while the dimension for the multi-channel LSTM model is channel-dependent.

Figure 2. Shape of input dimensions for single-channel (a) and multi-channel (b) ESD model.

2.3. Single- and Multi-Channel LSTM

The single-channel RNN-based epileptic seizure detection model applied here was first proposed by Hussein et al. [18] and includes three layers, as depicted in the lower part of Figure 3. An LSTM layer of 80 cells was used for deep feature learning to consider the long- and short-term dependencies of the time series EEG data. To avoid overfitting, a dropout layer of 0.25 was added. The learned features were fed into a time-distributed fully connected layer consisting of 50 units. The output was then passed through a one-dimensional average pooling layer so that all EEG segments were considered equally for the classification. Finally, a single sigmoid neuron uses the output of the pooling layer to classify each segment into ictal or inter-ictal.

Figure 3. Architectures of the used ESD models; a bidirectional LSTM layer with 40 units was used in combination with the CNN .

2.4. CNN-LSTM Model

The CNN part consists of three 2D layers followed by MaxPooling layers, as depicted in the upper part of Figure 3. The first 2D convolutional layer filters raw EEG data using 16×3 -kernels resulting in an output with two reduced samples of D and C , but with 16 additive frame images due to the 16 kernels. A following MaxPooling layer with size 2 pools the frame images preserving the maximum value of each 2-by-2 matrix and reduces the dimension of D and C by a factor of two, thereby also reducing the computational cost. The second and third convolutional layers consist of 32 and 64 kernels, respectively, while the following MaxPooling layers again use a 2-by-2 matrix. The resulting patterns are flattened and distributed in time afterward to obtain the correct input dimension to the LSTM part. The LSTM part of the model is built as explained in Section 2.3, whereas in this case a bidirectional LSTM (biLSTM) with 40 cells was used as Golmohammadi et al. [25] proposed.

For both models, raw EEG batches with the size of $N = 32$ samples were fed into the model. To implement an adaptive learning rate for quicker convergence during training, the initial learning rate was set to 0.001 and reduced with respect to the validation loss with a factor of 0.8. The binary cross-entropy was chosen as the loss function, and an Adam optimizer [26] was used as the gradient descent method. The single-channel model was trained for 40 epochs (as proposed in [18]), while the optimal number of training epochs for the multi-channel approaches was determined during the analysis of performance results.

2.5. Data Set Description and Processing

The University of Bonn provided the *EPItect* data set [27] containing EEG data from inpatients suffering from different types of epilepsy. EEG data contain artifacts since no artifact removal methods have been done. A total of 4340 h of 21-channel scalp EEG data (10–20 system) from 90 patients in 557 sessions were recorded with a sampling frequency of 256 Hz and 16 bits per sample. In 194 of these sessions (and for 68 of the 90 patients) epileptic seizures were actually recorded with a total duration of 6.4 h. EEG data were sighted and labeled by medical professionals, where labels comprised the following information: temporal position of the seizure onsets and offsets in combination with the epileptic state (ictal or inter-ictal). Seizure onset zones and the motor behavior of seizures, as well as patients' awareness during ictal phases, were noted. A total of 5% of the recorded seizures are generalized, 1% are hemispheric, 89% are focal seizures, and 5% could not be identified. The epileptogenic zone of 83% of focal seizures in the data set is located in the temporal lobe, 16% in the frontal lobe, and 1% in the parietal lobe. Apart from 7% unclassified seizures, the data set contains 48% FIAS, 38% FAS, and 6% tonic-clonic seizures.

A subset of the *EPItect* data set was used in this study: Table 2 gives an overview of the training and test data set. The duration of epileptic seizures is relatively short compared with the prolonged non-ictal phases, resulting in a natural imbalance in EEG data sets. To compensate for the strong imbalance of the ictal and inter-ictal classes, different balancing and data augmentation methods were applied and compared: over- and under-sampling, as well as window overlap and noise addition. The random under-sampling method [28] equalizes the data set by randomly excluding data samples from the majority class data, which has the drawback of reducing the variability of the majority class [29]. The over-sampling method [28] is characterized by multiplying the minority class data to adjust the class balance and leads to the exact opposite effect. By applying the window overlap method, minor class data samples were multiplied as well but each data frame was shifted in time by in this study 2.3 s leading to a window overlap of 90%. In this study, ictal state EEG data were augmented by adding white noise to each frame with a signal-to-noise ratio of 10 decibels. As the under-sampling method outperformed other data balancing methods in terms of F1 and FAR/h (see Table 3), EEG data were prepared as follows: Only session data containing ictal phases were used in the training set and data frames containing inter-ictal phases were randomly excluded from the data set. Based on pilot experiments, we chose an ictal to inter-ictal ratio of 2/3 as a trade-off between data balance and the amount of training samples.

Table 2. Size of training and test data set.

Training				Test			
42 Patients 8 h				14 Patients 101 h			
motor		non-motor		motor		non-motor	
27 Patients 5 h		15 Patients 3 h		5 Patients 60.5 h		9 Patients 40.5 h	
ictal	inter	ictal	inter	ictal	inter	ictal	inter
125 min	186 min	66 min	99 min	32 min	60 h	17 min	40 h

Table 3. Median results for the CNN-LSTM model using data augmentation methods for the training data set with channels B were referenced to \bar{B} .

Method	F1 Score	FAR/h	Sensitivity in %
Under-sampling	0.144	9.9	68.0
Over-sampling	0.091	10.9	61.5
Overlap	0.073	22.8	70.8
Noise addition	0.064	26.2	70.0

The complete EPItect data set contains 0.2% ictal phases, and it was used as the reference value for the percentage of ictal states in the test set. Finally, training and test data are disjunct with respect to patient identity, i.e., the test set does not contain any patient-specific data used in the training set. For the hyperparameter tuning, a 5-fold cross-validation [30] procedure was performed.

3. Results

Three types of recurrent neural networks have been used as models to detect epileptic seizures in raw scalp EEG data. Figures 4–6 show the classification performance on the test set in terms of sensitivity, false alarm rates per hour (FAR/h), and F1 scores for the proposed recurrent neural networks *CNN-LSTM* and *mLSTM* using BTE electrode channels T3 and T4, as well as *sLSTM* using only channel T4; results are reported for different sets of reference electrodes. To evaluate the classification performance, a bootstrapping procedure [31] was applied: 80% of all classified frames were randomly chosen to calculate each evaluation metric, which was repeated 1000 times. The resulting data were normally distributed; an analysis of variance and additional Bonferroni correction was performed to test for significant differences.

Figure 4. F1 scores, AUC values, sensitivity, and false alarms per hour (FAR/h) of the sLSTM model using signals of channel T4 for references \bar{A} , \bar{T} , \bar{B} , T3.

Figure 5. F1 scores, AUC values, sensitivity, and false alarms per hour (FAR/h) of the mLSTM model corresponding to each channel to reference combination.

Figure 6. F1 scores, AUC values, sensitivity, and false alarms per hour (FAR/h) of the CNN-LSTM model corresponding to each channel to reference combination.

3.1. Channel and Reference Analysis

For the single-channel baseline model (sLSTM) introduced by Hussein et al. [18], the results for different reference electrodes differ significantly. As presented in Figure 4, the model produces approximately 20 false alarms per hour when referencing the T4 channel signal to \bar{B} and \bar{B} . This false alarm rate could be reduced by referencing to \bar{A} ; however, this

condition also lowers the sensitivity to a median of 56% and produces an AUC value of 0.84, which is significantly lower than for the other conditions. When using the opposite channel T3 as a reference, the highest F1 score for this model is achieved (which is still low at 0.09), with a median sensitivity of 70% and FAR/h of 17.

Taking both BTE channels B into account by using the multi-channel LSTM model (see Figure 5) has a positive influence on the classification performance: Using the common average reference \bar{A} led to a significantly higher median F1 score of 0.15 with a corresponding false alarm rate below nine times per hour. However, the sensitivity for this channel-to-reference combination (median of 55%) is significantly lower than for almost every other condition. Channels T led to better sensitivity scores, but worse FAR/h, whereas AUC values do not differ significantly from B . With this model, median F1 scores above 0.1 or FAR/h below ten could not be achieved by using larger channel regions (T , C and A), indicating that the multi-channel LSTM model did not profit from inputs that correspond to a large coverage of the scalp.

In contrast to the mLSTM model, the F1 score could be increased with the CNN-LSTM when using all 21 channels of the 10–20 electrode system: As presented in Figure 6, the median F1 score reached 0.167 and less than ten false alarms per hour when electrode set A is used as input and referenced to \bar{B} . With this reference set, the sensitivity increased to 73% (i.e., by 5 percentage points) in comparison with using only B channel signals as input to the model. The lowest FAR/h (4.4) could be achieved by referencing T to \bar{A} which, on the other hand, drastically decreased the median sensitivity to 36%. By using reference \bar{T} , the sensitivity could be enhanced to 58% leading to the highest F1 score of 0.175 (significantly different from other values) with a corresponding median FAR of 6.4 times per hour. In terms of AUC values, this model achieved the best results with B referenced to \bar{T} and C referenced to \bar{B} . All input channel and reference conditions achieved a median AUC value of at least 0.85.

3.2. Single- and Multi-Channel Classification

Since we are especially interested in electrode configurations that could be used in future mobile scenarios, we analyzed the models with signals from behind-the-ear electrodes only, both as input (Set B) and reference (\bar{B}); results are shown in Figure 7. In terms of sensitivity, the CNN-LSTM model resulted in a median value that is significantly lower than for other combinations (68%) while the sLSTM model outperformed the others with a median value of 74%. The AUC values of the CNN-LSTM and the sLSTM model ($AUC = 0.92$) did not differ significantly but both models outperformed the mLSTM model ($AUC = 0.90$), which differed significantly. With this channel-to-reference condition and when using the baseline LSTM model [18] as a multi-channel approach, the F1 score was decreased slightly but significantly by 0.3 percentage points. The significantly highest F1 score with a median of 0.144 could be achieved by using the CNN-LSTM model which also produced the lowest median FAR/h of 9.9. Further analysis of the importance of motor and non-motor seizures was therefore carried out using this best-performing CNN-LSTM model with behind-the-ear electrodes.

Figure 7. F1 scores, AUC values, sensitivity, and false alarms per hour (FAR/h) of the proposed RNN models when using EEG signals of channels B referenced to \bar{B} .

3.3. Differences in the Classification of Motor and Non-Motor Seizures

Since different EEG databases for ESD contain different percentages of motor and non-motor seizures for training, we explore the effect of these two classes on ESD performance. Specifically, we test classification when training and testing with each class alone (matched training), training with one class and testing with the other (mismatched training), and using all available data, combining both seizure types. Hence, the ESD model was trained and tested with motor and non-motor seizures separately as well as combined data. Figure 8 shows the F1 scores, AUC value, sensitivity in %, and FAR/h when using the best-performing model (CNN-LSTM) with behind-the-ear electrodes only (as explained above). When training the model with motor and non-motor seizures, the classification performance differs significantly from results obtained from models with class-specific training: For the combined model, 73.6% of motor seizures and 57.1% of non-motor seizures were detected. Motor and non-motor seizures produced FARs of 1.3 and 23 per hour, respectively. Significantly more motor seizures were detected when training class-specific models (83% for motor-seizure training; 94% for non-motor-seizure training). At the same time, the FAR/h value was increased to 13.5 (motor) and 34 (non-motor) for the class-specific models. More non-motor seizures were detected when training the model only with non-motor seizures (around 78%); the FAR/h, however, also increased drastically (up to 46). Overall, motor seizures appear to be detected more reliably than non-motor seizures, whether or not the model has been trained with motor or non-motor seizures separately. The model does not profit from training with motor or non-motor seizures separately, on the contrary, the overall classification performance decreased.

Figure 8. Classification results of the CNN-LSTM model when considering motor (m), non-motor (n), and both (m and n) motor types in seizures in the training and test set. B channels were used and referenced to \bar{B} .

4. Discussion

The classification performances of automated ESD models based on RNNs were analyzed for raw scalp EEG signals from the EPItect data set [27]. Hussein et al. [18] proposed a single-channel LSTM-based model and used the Bonn data set consisting of 40 min ictal and 40 min non-ictal intracranial EEG data recorded from five epilepsy and five healthy patients, respectively. This data set was split into training and test sets and fed into an LSTM-based model, resulting in 100% detection accuracy on the validation set. The experiments presented in the current paper used a different data set (EPItect), for which a maximum F1 score of 0.09 was achieved (cf. Figure 4). With a median sensitivity value of 70% and 20 FAR/h, it appears that the specific modeling approach does not generalize well from the Bonn data set to the processing of scalp EEG.

Single- and Multi-Channel Classification: Using multiple channels for this model hardly enhances the performance: Though fewer false alarms were detected (see Section 3.1) and slightly higher F1 scores could be achieved, the sensitivity decreased to 55%. Thus, for the condition with the lowest FAR/h, almost every second ictal state was missed by the model. In the direct comparison (Section 3.2) to the single-channel approach, the multi-channel configuration achieved a lower sensitivity and a FAR/h that was only slightly lower. Therefore, using the proposed LSTM model in a multi-channel context does not lead to the desired performance enhancement. In contrast, there seems to be a disadvantage of considering too many channels as input to the model. Since this model considers each channel as one individual feature and some channel signals are hardly conjunct with seizure characteristics, the resulting inconsistency of signal patterns could lead to inaccurate detection performance. As the temporal lobe is the most common focal seizure onset zone [7], channels B and T contain most seizure signals which underlines this assumption through the benefit of using only BTE channels.

The additional CNN was used to contextualize all channel signals, which increased the F1 score to a maximum of 0.17 and simultaneously decreased the FAR/h to less than

five indicating an actual enhancement of the overall performance. The sensitivity, however, did not benefit through the additional CNN, resulting in many missed ictal states.

Channel and Reference Analysis: With regard to mobile devices, the influence of channel reduction especially in the temporal lobe area was considered. Gu et al. [8] evaluated the classification performances of an SVM-based ESD model with full-size EEG cap channels in comparison with behind-the-ear EEG electrodes and showed that BTE channels perform better in the presence of many eye-blinking artifacts. By applying canonical correlation analysis muscle artifacts in the EEG signals have been removed. With this patient-specific approach, Gu et al. [8] achieved a median false alarm rate of 0.52 per hour and a median sensitivity of 94.50%. We therefore expected the temporal lobe channels to produce good ESD performances. Additionally, TLE is the most common focal seizure type [32], and these channels deliver the most information on the activity in this brain area.

Results for our patient-independent approach show that the best F1 score could be achieved using channel set T referenced to \bar{T} , which also produces a relatively low FAR/h. In total, 58% of the ictal states were detected in this condition; when set B was used and referenced to \bar{B} , 68% of the ictal states were detected with a mean FAR/h below ten. These results indicate that EEG channels near the temporal lobe channels are especially suitable for seizure detection. When using the channels closest to the ear (set B , reference \hat{B}), results that approach the best performance were obtained. In this study, channels B were considered since these are the only electrodes available resembling those of mobile EEG devices. Although measurements were conducted with clinical hardware, the specifications in terms of bit depth (16) and sampling frequency (256 Hz) are also available with mobile EEG amplifiers. We therefore assume that additional electrodes placed very close to the ear, as present in mobile EEG devices (and hence in a scalp region with very low hair density and potentially lower impedance), might increase the SNR, and the signal quality in general, helping with overall performance. However, if such a system is used in daily life, artifacts from movement will have a large impact, which should be investigated in a future study. In addition, as the majority (83%) of the data set contains TLE, future studies should investigate the classification performance of TLE in comparison with other epilepsy types.

Differences in the Classification of Motor and Non-Motor Seizure: To compare the classification performance of motor and non-motor seizures, we tested the CNN-LSTM model, which was trained with motor and non-motor seizures, with data containing each motor characteristic separately. Results show that more motor seizures were detected than non-motor seizures, as shown on the left-hand side of Figure 8. In addition, 92.4% of all falsely detected seizures were non-motor seizures. A possible explanation might be the imbalance in terms of the size of these two data sets: the model was trained with a larger amount of motor than non-motor seizure data (see Table 2), which should have resulted in a model primarily tailored to motor seizure classification. Due to the very different signal characteristics of motor and non-motor seizure data, we assume that a potential solution could be the training of separate classifiers that are each specialized on each type of seizure, and a simple integration stage on top of the two classification results (i.e., a simple logical OR operation).

Training the models with motor and non-motor seizures individually caused a reduction in the overall performance in terms of the F1 score. We find it interesting that the classification performance for non-motor seizures did not benefit from training the model with non-motor seizures only: the F1 score for the model trained on non-motor seizures does not differ significantly from the model trained with motor seizures. For each training condition, non-motor seizure detection rates are significantly lower compared with motor seizures. When using the EPItect data set, we therefore assume that the dominating factor

for overall performance is not the signal characteristics of motor seizures but the amount of data per signal category.

Data Set Limitations: Due to the variability in signal characteristics regarding seizure types and patient dependencies, a large amount of data representing this variability to train a deep learning model is crucial, especially for generalizing patient-independent models. The overall training data passed through the models proposed in this work consisted of around 9 h of scalp EEG data from 42 patients with an inter-ictal to ictal ratio of 2:1. In total, 100 h of data from 14 patients with highly imbalanced classes were used to test the model performance. Therefore, it is still unclear if the detection performance for non-motor seizures could benefit by training the model with non-motor seizures alone but using the same amount of data. However, this seizure type does not occur as often as motor seizures reducing the amount of data for this class at the same time. It would be very interesting to increase the variability of the data, especially for non-motor seizures since this could increase the overall class-specific scoring; this could be achieved by adding non-motor seizures from other data sets. We did not include such an analysis here since—at the time of performing the experiments—such a database compatible with our requirements (matching number of EEG channels and labels for non-motor seizures) did not exist. In open-source epilepsy data sets, such as the Temple University EEG Corpus [23] or the Bonn data set [19], the motor characteristics of seizures are not documented. Given the results of our study, we believe this information to be a valuable addition to the collection of future EEG data sets with a focus on epilepsy detection.

Nonetheless, detecting non-motor seizures still is quite challenging, but as most ($\sim 2/3$) of the non-motor seizures in this data set are FAS, and 73.8% of FAS were correctly documented by humans in the study by Hoppe et al. [2], the focus might not necessarily lie on the detection of non-motor seizures. On the other hand, as 72% of motor seizures are FIAS, and only 26.8% of FIAS were correctly documented by humans [2], the presented ESD model outperformed seizure diaries.

For classification performance, the type of seizure in terms of the involved brain region(s) could be relevant. In the data set used in this study, most seizures correspond to temporal lobe epilepsy (TLE). The proportion of TLE seizures in the non-motor data is 80% (training) and 96% (test). For the motor data, these values are 100% (training) and 52% (test). The remaining seizures of the latter set have been labeled as “unknown” type. It is therefore not clear how well our approach is suited for seizure classification with different onset regions, and due to the limited data, it was not possible to explore other patient-specific splits of the EPITect data. This should be explored in future research with an alternative data set.

Golmohammadi et al. [25] used the largest openly accessible seizure-based data set TUEG [23] for their CNN-LSTM-based automatic seizure detection models. A low false alarm rate of six times per day could be achieved with this approach which, however, produces relatively low sensitivity scores (30.83%). We assume that a larger data set also leads to an improvement in generalization not only regarding inpatient dependencies but also to seizure-type-specific dependencies. This is in line with the assumption that the reduction in classification performance for the model trained with motor and non-motor seizures actually might be caused by the reduction in training data in general.

Finally, the results presented in this study are based on clinically collected scalp EEG data that do not factor in artifacts that arise in mobile BTE EEG devices from the users’ movement. While the aim of this paper is to explore seizure detection with little additional information about the user based on raw input data, it can be assumed that model performance could be increased through several measures that should be explored in future research: artifact reduction should be beneficial, especially when using data sets containing

muscle and head movements from real-world recordings; adapting an existing model with a limited amount of data collected from the individual could improve model performance, as well as an individual threshold that requires consecutive positives before a seizure is actually logged. Another approach to partially compensate for this matter could be the usage of a multi-modal model [33] using biomedical data that could detect highly elevated heartbeat (captured through electrocardiography or photoplethysmography) or respiratory frequency [34,35] which coincide with seizures but not necessarily with everyday activities.

To avoid a bias in the models due to the under-representation of ictal state data, we used the under-sampling method to balance the data set. This, however, leads to a significant reduction in the overall data size. A multi-modal approach [33] could not only compensate for the reduction in the overall data size but also address the imbalance of seizure type data, as given for instance with motor and non-motor seizures. Another approach to address the influence of imbalanced or underrepresented data could be the application of data augmentation methods to EEG data, which should be considered in future studies.

General Discussion: In general, a perfect ESD system has not been developed yet, as there is always a trade-off between sensitivity and the amount of false alarms. A possibility to reduce the false alarm rate and therefore enhance the system is to only declare a detected ictal state sample as seizure if also the next (few) samples are detected as ictal as well. Although sensitivity and false alarm rates (FAR) reported in this paper could be improved with the proposed approach over the baseline, the performance is still below what is desired in clinical applications; further, the 68% sensitivity with BTE electrodes is too low for reliable seizure detection in everyday scenes, and motion artifacts which would negatively affect the scoring have not been considered. The research presented here is therefore a step towards clinical and wearable solutions that sheds light on crucial design decisions, such as electrode location, the effect of training data, and consequences for motor and non-motor seizures.

5. Conclusions

In this work, different RNN-based deep learning models were examined for a patient-independent automatic ESD: an LSTM model approach was used in a single-channel and a multi-channel context, which was additionally augmented by a CNN architecture. Different electrode and reference configurations were used as input to these model types to study the importance of covering specific regions of the scalp for ESP. Specifically, a few electrode configurations near the ear were explored to approximate electrode coverage that is available for mobile setups for which wearing a full-size EEG cap is not feasible and behind-the-ear hardware could be used. Results show that 68% of ictal states could be documented with behind-the-ear electrodes, with a false alarm rate of 10 times per hour when using the multi-channel CNN-LSTM model. This model outperforms the single-channel approach for seizure detection for all electrode configurations under investigation, with the full 10–20 electrode channels producing the best scores considering the sensitivity (73%) and FAR/h (9.9). These findings could guide future developments for clinical and wearable solutions that reliably allow the detection of epileptic seizures in everyday life.

Due to the highly different signal characteristics of motor and non-motor seizures, we used either signal type and both types combined for training and quantified the impact on model performance. We found that motor seizures are detected more reliably than non-motor seizures independently of the training paradigm. Training the model with both motor and non-motor seizure data results in a lower false alarm rate and an F1 score above 0.5. Splitting the training data set regarding the motor characteristics did not enhance the performance on the respective test set; we assume this could be linked

to the reduced amount of data for class-specific training. Our results show that signal properties associated with motor and non-motor seizures play a role in seizure classification. We therefore recommend that this specific information should be added to future EEG databases for epilepsy research.

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Abbreviations

The following abbreviations are used in this manuscript:

FIAS	focal impaired awareness seizures
FAS	focal awareness seizures
ESD	epileptic seizure detection
EEG	electroencephalography
BTE	behind-the-ear
TLE	temporal lobe epilepsy
DNN	deep neural network
CNN	convolutional neural network
RNN	recurrent neural network
LSTM	a long short-term memory
sLSTM	single-channel LSTM
mMSTL	multi-channel LSTM

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